

Peroxomonosulfuric acid oxidations : kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of *N*-methylaniline

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The oxidation of *N*-methylaniline by peroxomonosulfuric acid (PMSA) obeys second order kinetics – first order each in [PMSA] and [*N*-methylaniline] at constant pH. The observed pH-rate profile has been rationalized by invoking various PMSA species and the unprotonated form of the amine as reactive species; the reactivities of these species have been estimated. The mechanism of oxidation involves the nucleophilic attack of amine lone-pair on the electrophilic peroxy oxygen. *N*-Methylaniline reacts at a faster rate with PMSA species than *N,N*-dimethylaniline.

Oxidation of organic nitrogen compounds using peracids has been the subject of interest over many years¹⁻⁶. Tertiary amines react with peracids yielding amine oxides while primary and secondary amines give mixed products on oxidation⁴. Condensation reactions give byproducts. Recently we have reported the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aminobenzoic acids⁷ and pyridine⁸ by peroxomonosulfuric acid. As a part of our continuing interest in peroxidation mechanisms, we present here a kinetic study of oxidation of *N*-methylaniline by peroxomonosulfuric acid (PMSA) in the pH-range 0–5 at different temperatures. The relative reactivities of HSO₅⁻ and SO₅²⁻ in the reaction, have been estimated. It was found that the peroxomonosulfuric acid species reacted at a lower rate than those of peroxomonophosphoric acid (PMPA) with *N*-methylaniline³. For the purpose of comparison, we have undertaken the pH-rate study of *N,N*-dimethylaniline – PMSA reaction also in aqueous acetonitrile (50%, v/v) at different temperatures.

Results and Discussion

Rate constants for different concentrations of peroxomonosulfuric acid and *N*-methylaniline at constant ionic strength and [H⁺] are presented in Table 1. The oxidation follows the second order rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [N\text{-methylaniline}]_t [\text{PMSA}]_t \quad (1)$$

where k_{obs} is the second order rate constant and t the total concentration.

The oxidation rate is found to be insensitive to the variation of ionic strength of the medium using NaClO₄, and also to the addition of acrylamide (Table 1). The rate of oxidation is found to decrease with an increase in the acetonitrile content in the solvent mixture (Table 1).

The kinetics of oxidation of *N*-methylaniline by PMSA

Table 1 Second order rate constants for the oxidation of *N*-methylaniline by peroxomonosulfuric acid

Temp = 308 K, acetonitrile water = 20 80 (v/v), [H ⁺] = 0.1 mol dm ⁻³ , μ = 0.2 mol dm ⁻³			
Substrate	<i>N</i> -methylaniline		
10 ³ [S] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ [PMSA] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k_1' s ⁻¹	10 ³ k_2' dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
4.1	4.1	4.43	10.8
9.0	2.4	9.71	10.7
15.0	2.4	15.3	10.1
20.0	4.8	20.9	10.4
15.3	1.5	17.5	11.4
15.3	3.2	17.5	11.4
17.6	5.7	20.5	11.6
15.3	1.6	18.6	12.1 ^a
15.2	4.9	17.0	11.2 ^b
16.8	5.2	24.4	14.5 ^c
15.9	5.0	7.84	4.93 ^d

^aμ = 0.4 mol dm⁻³ ^b[acrylamide] = 4.9 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ ^cAcetonitrile water = 10 90 % (v/v) ^dAcetonitrile water = 40 60 % (v/v) water = 10 90 % (v/v) ^eAcetonitrile water = 40 60 % (v/v)

have been investigated in the pH range 0–5 and at 308, 318 and 328 K. The rate data are summarized in Table 2. The rate increases with increase in pH. Activation parameters for the reaction have been computed from the linear plot of log k_2' against T^{-1} and were found to be $E_a = 11.8$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 46.8$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -58.9$ J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

The pH-rate study of *N,N*-dimethylaniline – PMSA reaction in aqueous acetonitrile (50%, v/v) was also carried out in the pH range 0–5 (Table 2) at different temperatures (308–328 K). The energy of activation for the reaction was found to be 12.1 kJ mol⁻¹. ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were estimated to

Table 2 Second order rate constants for the oxidation of *N*-methylaniline and *N,N*-dimethylaniline by peroxomonosulfuric acid at different pH^a

Substrate	pH	10 ³ k ₂ , dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹		
		308	318	328 K
<i>N</i> -Methylaniline ^d	0 00	0 93 (0 91)	1 27 (1 54)	2 27 (3 01)
	0 32	1 55 (1 80)	2 79 (3 09)	5 88 (6 03)
	0 69	3 56 (4 50)	5 82 (6 18)	12 3 (12 1)
	1 00	11 4 (9 01)	15 4 (15 4)	32 4 (30 1)
	2 00	123 (90 0)	150 (154)	430 (300)
	3 42	977 (2284)	1200 (1523)	2915 (4569)
	4 52	3231 (20366)	8814 (32782)	– –
	5 20	7970 (44320)	13375 (78700)	– –
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylaniline ^b	0 00	0 33 (0 33)	0 54 (0 56)	1 22 (1 30)
	0 32	0 65 (0 66)	0 89 (1 11)	1 65 (2 60)
	0 69	1 32 (1 64)	3 63 (2 79)	8 74 (6 50)
	1 00	2 93 (3 28)	5 31 (5 59)	11 0 (13 0)
	1 30	6 5 (6 5)	13 6 (11 2)	23 8 (25 9)
	2 00	22 0 (32 6)	41 7 (55 8)	73 5 (129)
	3 40	265 (773)	604 (1639)	997 (38096)
	4 90	1995 (8686)	3030 (13660)	4034 (22917)

*Values in parentheses represent 10³ k₂ (calcd) dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹

^aCH₃CN water = 20 80 (v/v) ^bCH₃CN water = 50 50 (v/v)

be 47.9 kJ mol⁻¹ and -68.7 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively.

Rate law and mechanism :

In the pH range studied both *N*-methylaniline and *N,N*-dimethylaniline exist in neutral (S) as well as in protonated (SH⁺) forms,

where K_a = 1.4 × 10⁻⁵ and 2.5 × 10⁻⁵ for *N*-methylaniline⁹ and *N,N*-dimethylaniline¹, respectively.

In peroxomonosulfuric acid¹⁰ (HO-SO₃H), one proton

is a sulfuric acid proton and the other a hydrogen peroxide proton. The pK value of the sulfuric acid proton lies in the high acidity region while the hydrogen peroxide proton has a pK₁ value of 9.4, thus indicating that in the pH range studied PMSA exists as HSO₅⁻ and SO₅²⁻.

The various steps involved in the oxidation of *N*-methylaniline and *N,N*-dimethylaniline by PMSA in the explored range of pH may, therefore, be represented by eqns. (3) – (5),

We do not envisage oxidation steps to include the protonated amine species (SH⁺) for the reason that peracids react with electron pair donors by nucleophilic displacement on peroxide oxygen¹¹.

In the present study, the general observations of second order kinetics, the decrease of rate with decreasing solvent polarity, high negative entropy of activation and activation energies in the range 11.8–12.1 kcal mol⁻¹ provide evidence for the reactions to involve nucleophilic displacement on the electrophilic peroxo-oxygen¹²

The rate law pertaining to the reaction steps, eqns. (3) – (5) is

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} = k_1[\text{HSO}_5^-][\text{S}] + k_2[\text{SO}_5^{2-}][\text{S}] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where, } [\text{PMSA}]_t = [\text{HSO}_5^-] + [\text{SO}_5^{2-}] \quad (7)$$

The total analytical concentration of amine, [S]_t is given as

$$[\text{S}]_t = [\text{S}] + [\text{SH}^+] \quad (8)$$

From eqns. (2), (3), (6)–(8), we have

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} = \left\{ \frac{k_1 K_a [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_1 K_a}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])(K_a + [\text{H}^+])} \right\} [\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{S}]_t \quad (9)$$

or

$$k_2' = \frac{k_1 K_a [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_1 K_a}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])(K_a + [\text{H}^+])} \quad (10)$$

The average values of k₁ at 308, 318 and 328 K obtained by least-squares analysis of the data (Table 2) according to eqn. (10) are respectively 64.3, 110 and 215 dm³

$\text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ for *N*-methylaniline, and 13, 22.3 and $51.8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for *N,N*-dimethylaniline. The value of k_2 in both the cases is very small and negative and, therefore, has been approximated to zero. Hence, the rate expression (10) reduces to the form,

$$k_2' = \frac{k_1 K_a [\text{H}^+]}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])(K_a + [\text{H}^+])} \quad (11)$$

Eqn. (11) has been used for calculating the rate constants, k_2 (Table 2).

The reactivity order $\text{HSO}_5^- > \text{SO}_5^{2-}$ is quite in consonance with the electrophilic behavior of PMSA species¹³ in the reaction. The lower reactivity of *N,N*-dimethylaniline as compared to *N*-methylaniline (despite the fact that the former has higher electron density on amino-nitrogen as compared to the monomethyl derivative) may be attributed to the steric factor which has a destabilizing influence on the transition state¹⁴.

In the oxidation of dimethylanilines by Caro's acid, Ogata and Tabushi¹⁵ ruled out the species HSO_5^- , SO_5^{2-} and SH^+ , and postulated the reaction to be between the neutral molecules such as H_2SO_5 and S. This conclusion was based on the fact that added salt Na_2SO_4 had little effect on the reaction rate.

Basing on the experimental observations, the rate law and the literature reports², we envisage the reaction to involve a rate-determining nucleophilic attack of the amine lone-pair on the electrophilic peroxy-oxygen of HSO_5^- , giving rise to a S_N2 type transition state (I),

from which hydroxymethyl aniline is expected to result in the rate-determining step. The phenylhydroxylamine in the presence of H^+ , however, rearranges to form the corresponding *p*-aminophenol¹⁶. In the *N*-methylaniline-peroxomonophosphoric acid reaction also Panigrahi and Nayak³ reported *p*-aminophenol as the product.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of the solutions. The potassium salt of Caro's acid, oxone ($2\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot \text{KHSO}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$) (Dupont) was used to prepare PMSA solutions. Acetonitrile was distilled over P_2O_5 (b.p. $81-82^\circ$). *N*-

Methylaniline and *N,N*-dimethylaniline were distilled before use. Sodium perchlorate was used for adjusting the ionic strength.

The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions. The progress of the reactions was followed by iodometric determination of the unreacted oxidant present in the aliquots of the reaction mixture at different time intervals. All the kinetic runs were carried out in duplicate, the results being reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$. The temperature was constant to within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Product study : *N*-Methylaniline (0.136 g, 1.27 mmol) was dissolved in aqueous acetonitrile (80–20%, v/v; 50 ml) containing $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$, and to it oxone (0.070 g, 0.114 mmol) was added. The mixture was then stirred and allowed to stand overnight at 35° .

A few drops of the test solution were treated with a little solid chloramine-T in presence of hydrochloric acid. After a few minutes the ether extract of the above mixture was brought in contact with a filter paper moistened with an ether solution of phenol. Appearance of a blue stain when the fleck was exposed to ammonia vapour indicated *p*-aminophenol as one of the products of oxidation¹⁷.

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